
Teacher Education in India: An analysis in the context of the National Education Policy, 2020

Dr. Mohit Dixit

Head, Department of Education, Parishkar College of Global Excellence (Autonomous), Mansarovar, Jaipur, Rajasthan, Email- drmdsir21@gmail.com

Dr. Sunita Saini

Head, Department of Political Science, Parishkar College of Global Excellence (Autonomous) Mansarovar, Jaipur, Rajasthan, drsunitasaini07@gmail.com

Khushboo Dixit

Student (PG Final Year), Poddar International College, Mansarovar, Jaipur, Rajasthan

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ABSTRACT

Teacher education is the backbone of the education system of any country. Its direction and condition determine the nature of school education and how the national educational objectives will be met. Teacher education is responsible for the education and practice of skilled and qualified teachers. India has a rich cultural heritage and developed knowledge traditions in its history, under which there is a lot of evidence related to education and teacher education. In the journey from history to the present, India has seen profound changes in education as well as teacher education. The National Education Policy, 2020 represents these changes meaningfully, which is a revolutionary initiative in the education system of India. The National Education Policy, 2020 proposes some major reforms in the field of teacher education and seeks to reorient the existing system of teacher education. The present article analyses the changes taking place in teacher education in India in the light of the National Education Policy, 2020 and explores the role of the National Council for Teacher

Education (NCTE) in these changes. This article also discusses the changing meanings of teacher education in the context of educational changes in India.

Introduction

India has been a country of Guru-Shishya tradition since time immemorial. Education is considered as an essential human skill in the culture and social structure here. Our Vedas, Vedangas which are scriptures based on a rich intellectualism and contemplation; He has always guided us in the subject of teaching-learning. The contribution of the Gurus has been the most in taking our rich and rich knowledge tradition to the common man. But during the development journey of different periods, a lot of things happened, which greatly limited the place and role of Gurus in the country of India and we kept moving away from our rich knowledge tradition. In the present times, the journey of reconnecting with our rich knowledge traditions has begun. The contribution of the National Education Policy, 2020 in this journey is incomparable. The National Education Policy, 2020 proposed a radical change in the entire education system of the country, under which an attempt was made to look at teacher education from a new perspective. In keeping with this effort, the National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) has also accelerated the efforts to turn the direction and condition of teacher education in the country towards a positive change and has made revisional and transformational efforts to realize the vision of a developed India by 2047. The present article presents an analysis of the efforts of the National Education Policy, 2020 and the National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) and identifies the various stages of the development of teacher education in India.

If we try to understand the development of teacher education in India in brief, we can easily identify its earliest evidence in the Vedic era. The history of teacher education in India has been rich and diverse, reflecting the values of the nation and its changing educational, social and cultural environment. The present form of teacher education in India has gone through several phases of history. It has been shaped by colonial influences, national policies, and global trends, from the ancient Gurukul system to the contemporary digital age. In ancient times, the Gurukul system served as the dominant educational structure in India. In this system, students called disciples lived with their teachers, known as gurus, in residential environments, often isolated from normal social life. This education system emphasized comprehensive education, which included scriptures, philosophy, military strategy, governance, and business skills. Education was present in both formal and informal forms, with teachers playing an important role in conveying knowledge and beliefs. The trainee approach was prevalent in this era, as

qualified teachers used to gain knowledge by satsang their gurus. In the Gurukul education system, there was an attempt to make students proficient in subjects such as grammar, mathematics, astronomy and literature, as well as religious education (Shanwal, 2023). If we talk about the pedagogy of the Vedic period in particular, the teaching method was mainly based on the oral tradition, under which education was acquired in a meaningful way through attentive listening to the Guru, chanting mantras and dialogue. If understood succinctly, the methods of listening, contemplation and nididhyasana were present at the core of this pedagogy (Shastri, 1903) (Das, 1931).

Similarly, if we try to trace the references to teacher education from about the tenth century to the eighteenth century, we easily find that indigenous schools developed in a highly developed form during this period. Formal and non-formal education began in these schools, with mathematics, science, grammar and literature being taught as major subjects (Kapoor, 2018). These students would later educate other students under the leadership of their teacher. The training of teachers during this period was informal, with educationists guiding aspiring teachers (Hassani, 2023).

In an attempt to understand the development of formal teacher education, when we try to refer to teacher education in India during the British colonial era, we find that the education system underwent major changes during this period, including teacher education (Basu 1982). However, no new education system emerged during this period, but in a planned manner, Western educational structures replaced indigenous and cultural education systems, and professional teacher-training institutes were established (Hazra, 2018). By the end of the 19th century, a number of teacher training colleges had been established by both government and private organizations, whose curriculum was basically rooted in Western values. Under this, there was a lot of emphasis on teaching, classroom management and discipline-specific expertise in teacher education.

After independence in 1947, India faced the challenge of establishing a comprehensive education system. Teacher education emerged as an important priority to guarantee quality education for the growing population (Kabir, 1953). Teacher education programmes were incorporated in institutions to enhance academic standards. Organizations such as the National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) were established for meaningful and relevant development of curriculum and teacher training materials (Mukherjee, 1965). In the context of teacher education, the formation of the Kothari Commission and its recommendations were an important milestone in the development of Indian education. The Commission deeply underlined the professional advancement of teachers and paved the way for working on measures to enhance teacher education to ensure its alignment with the national

development objective (Kapoor 2018). The Kothari Commission in its detailed report recommended pre-service and in-service teacher training programmes. In this sequence, the creation and development of the National Council for Teacher Education gave impetus to the development of teacher education in India. As a statutory body, the National Council for Teacher Education emerged as the principal authority for regulating and standardizing teacher education in India. This institution established norms and standards for teacher training institutes and courses. Accordingly, the National Policy on Education (NPE) 1986 laid emphasis on ensuring professional development of teachers as an essential element of educational reform. It recommended sustainable professional development, integration of technology in teacher training and better infrastructure for training institutes. Through all these efforts, the Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) course established itself as the requisite certification for a secondary school teacher. The National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) has efficiently managed other programmes related to teacher education.

Progress over the past years

In order to enhance the quality of teacher education in India and make it relevant in the present era, the Council for Teacher Education comprehensively revised its standards in the year 2014 under which a two-year B.Ed. program was implemented. The objective of this amendment was to provide more comprehensive training and practical experience to prospective teachers and at the same time to regulate the functioning of institutions working in the field of teacher education. Recent trends in teacher education show a major shift from traditional teacher-centered education to learner-centered education. The teaching-learning process has come a long way from "what is to be taught" to "how to be taught". (Schreyers and Dumbravenu, 2014). In order to improve the quality of education, it is very important to link teacher education with classroom teaching. The last few decades have seen a huge shift from teacher training to teacher education in terms of content and structure (Panigrahi, 2021).

National Education Policy: An Unprecedented Initiative

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is a comprehensive framework developed by the Government of India for fundamental reforms in the education system of the country. Approved on July 29, 2020, this policy replaces the previous education policy of 1986, making it the first major educational reform in three decades. The basic objective of NEP is to transform the Indian education landscape to meet the expectations of the 21st century while staying connected with its tradition, inspiring creativity, critical thinking and life-long learning. The National Education Policy (NEP), 2020 is a revolutionary project created by the Government of India to reform and transform the education sector of the country.

This policy is guided by principles that promote diversity, innovation, creativity, and comprehensive development in education (Malik, 2021). These guiding principles aim to prepare learners for the challenges of the 21st century while safeguarding India's cultural and historical ethos.

National Education Policy, 2020 and its core values

Every academic document is guided by some fundamental objectives in its basic structure and these objectives determine the principles in relation to a document within the context of which that document is to proceed. Regarding the National Education Policy, many such objectives were outlined, which are very important to fulfill in the journey of the country's development. These objectives include formulating an education policy that is able to develop an inclusive, meaningful, relevant, quality and holistic education system in the country. The National Education Policy, 2020 was developed after the efforts of the government, a large group of experts and scholars who worked hard. When we analyse the basic document of this education policy, we are able to easily identify the values in the light of which this policy has been framed and which it wants to inculcate in the education system of the country. The following are the key values endorsed by the NEP, 2020:

Comprehensive and Multidisciplinary Education

The National Education Policy, 2020 outlines the holistic development of conceptualization of students through encouraging a multidisciplinary framework. Rather than focusing solely on academic outcomes, it aims to combine arts, humanities, and business disciplines with science and mathematics. This work ethic enhances creativity, critical thinking, and flexibility in students. The National Education Policy, 2020 promotes lifelong learning and diversified employment opportunities in higher education by providing multiple entry and exit points along with multidisciplinary courses (Aithal, 2020)

Equality and Inclusion

Inclusion is a fundamental principle and value of the National Education Policy, 2020. This policy emphasizes the need to guarantee that every child, regardless of socio-economic status, gender, or geographical location, has access to quality education. In these ways, the policy seems committed to making education equitable for all. In light of these efforts, the policy endorses specific measures to promote equality for marginalized groups, including Scheduled Castes (SCs), Scheduled Tribes (STs), Other Backward Classes (OBCs), minorities, and persons with disabilities. This policy is also reflected in its efforts to promote gender equality in education through financial assistance and targeted programmes (National Policy on Education, 2020, page 38).

Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE)

The National Policy on Education, 2020 recognizes the critical importance of early childhood education, and recommends the inclusion of ECCE in the formal education framework for children between the ages of 3 and 6 years, as it seeks to take advantage of the critical brain development time in children. This policy recognizes that quality early childhood care and education can lay the foundation for lifelong good health, learning success, social emotional development, and economic output. By emphasizing play-based and experience-based learning, it fosters the qualities of curiosity, discovery, and enjoyable learning in young children. The structure of "5+3+3+4" guarantees that the first five years will be focused on developing the child's fundamental language and numerical skills (Malik, 2021 page – 1).

Adaptability and Choice

The National Education Policy, 2020 encourages flexibility in learning pathways in line with contemporary educational principles. It promotes students by allowing them to choose subjects according to their interests and abilities. This principle motivates learners to follow their interests and reduces the barriers to inflexible curriculum structures. The policy recognizes that vocational training should be integrated into the curriculum from an early age, thereby promoting skill-based learning and enhancing employability (NEP, 2020, pp. 19, 61-62).

Protection and promotion of Indian culture and heritage

The NEP, 2020 emphasizes on the preservation and promotion of India's extensive cultural heritage. It promotes the integration of local and regional art, history, and knowledge systems into the curriculum. The policy seeks to enhance students' engagement with their cultural heritage and improve cognitive development through promoting bilingual education and mother tongue instruction at the fundamental level (National Education Policy, 2020, p. 10). 86) 1

Technological Integration and Digital Education

The National Education Policy, 2020 underscores the need to incorporate technology in education due to the growing importance of digital literacy. The push for digital education encompasses the advancement of online and blended educational approaches to guarantee continuity of learning , especially during emergencies such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The National Education Policy recommends the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI), coding, and emerging technologies to enhance the relevance of education in the digital age (National Education Policy, 2020, page – 92).

Teacher Development and Empowerment

The NEP, 2020 recognizes teachers as the foundation of the education system and emphasizes on continuous professional development and empowerment of teachers. It also recommends the creation of comprehensive teacher-training frameworks and consistent assessment methods. This policy seeks to enhance the reputation of teaching as a profession by guaranteeing better working conditions, professional development opportunities and promotion on the basis of merit.

Environmental Consciousness and Sustainability

The NEP, 2020 emphasizes the need to include environmental education and sustainability as the foundational elements of the curriculum. It emphasises on creating awareness about environmental issues and the importance of sustainable lifestyles from a young age (NEP, 2020, p. 15).

Assessment for Learning

A fundamental aspect of the National Education Policy, 2020 is a shift from rote learning and high-pressure exams to creative assessment, which promotes critical thinking and practical application of knowledge. Continuous assessment promotes holistic child development and reduces exam anxiety (National Education Policy, 2020, pp. 26-29).

Global Citizenship and Ethical Principles

The National Education Policy, 2020 promotes the development of moral ideals, empathy and tolerance of diversity, which are important values for global citizenship. The policy recognizes that character development, ethical thinking and community participation should be given priority during the educational experience of students. The National Education Policy, 2020 reflects a progressive approach, emphasizing important ideals for the development of responsible, innovative and compassionate people. The policy seeks to transform India's educational environment by promoting holistic development, inclusion, sustainability, and technological integration, leading to a value-driven and inclusive society (National Education Policy, 2020, p. 15).

National Education Policy and Teacher Education

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 aims to bring about fundamental reforms in India's education system, with teacher education as a central element. The policy acknowledges the essential role of teachers in influencing the future of the nation and outlines strategies for their training, professional

development and improving working conditions. It underscores the need for competent, skilled, motivated, and empowered teachers to foster inclusive, engaging, and effective learning environments. NEP recognizes that the potential of education is intrinsically linked to the quality of teacher training. As a result, it recommends reforms to teacher-education programs, recruitment processes, and professional development systems (Fursavan 2024 page-775-6). It is a detailed analysis of the essential elements of NEP 2020 related to teacher-education .

Formation of Multidisciplinary Teacher-Education Institutes (TEIs)

The National Education Policy, 2020 recommends the creation of high-caliber multidisciplinary Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) across the country. These institutes will provide intensive and comprehensive teacher-education programs, combining subject-matter expertise with instructional methods and hands-on training. To promote accessibility and geographical equity under this policy, Teacher Education Institutes (TEIs) will be created or augmented in each district, facilitating greater access to teacher-education for future teachers (Gomathy, 2022).

Integration of the four-year comprehensive education graduate program (Bachelor of Education program)

One of the important recommendations of the National Education Policy, 2020 is the establishment of a four-year integrated B.Ed. curriculum by 2030. This program will provide the minimum prerequisites for academic positions in schools. The comprehensive course content strives to encompass expertise, pedagogical strategies, and experiential learning. This effort will provide hands-on training through internships, classroom simulations, and guidance from experienced teachers. This framework aims to develop skilled teachers in managing various classroom scenarios and employing innovative pedagogical techniques (Malik, 2021 p.3).

Comprehensive and Interdisciplinary Methodology in Teacher Education

The National Education Policy, 2020 underlines the need for teacher-education programmes to be multidisciplinary and comprehensive. Aspiring teachers will join courses in arts, sciences, social sciences, and business disciplines to develop a comprehensive understanding of educational concepts and situations. The programme will include elements such as communication skills, emotional intelligence, ethics and values, to prepare well-developed and skilled teachers (National Education Policy, 2020 pages 57-8).

Continuing Professional Development (CPD)

The National Education Policy, 2020 emphasizes the importance of lifelong learning and continuous professional development for teachers. All teachers must complete at least 50 hours of Continuing Professional Development (CPD) each year, which may include workshops, online courses, or participation in professional learning communities. CPD programs will be designed to assist teachers in staying abreast of contemporary pedagogical methodologies, technological innovations, and discipline-specific expertise.

National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST)

The policy advocates for the formulation of National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST) by the National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) in collaboration with stakeholders. These standards will outline abilities and performance criteria for teachers at different career stages. The NPST will act as a guiding framework for teacher-education institutions, ensuring uniformity and quality in teacher preparation related programs.

Recruitment and Professional Advancement

The National Education Policy, 2020 outlines competency-based and open processes for teacher recruitment. It advocates the abolition of contractual appointments and regularization of teaching positions to guarantee job stability and increase motivation. Career advancement will be linked to professional development and performance, giving teachers the possibility to hold leadership positions or specialize in areas such as curriculum creation and educational research, (National Education Policy, 2020 page – 35).

Use of Technology in Teacher Training

The National Education Policy, 2020 recognizes the transformative potential of technology in teacher training. The online platform will be used to provide accessible and cost-effective teacher training programs, especially for teachers located in remote areas. Blended learning methods, virtual simulations and digital assessments will be incorporated into teacher-education programmes to improve teaching effectiveness and engagement (National Education Policy, 2020 p. 95-6).

Focus on Inclusive and Value-Focused Education

The National Education Policy, 2020 emphasizes the need to equip teachers to manage various classrooms and promote inclusive education. The teacher-education programmes will focus on raising

awareness among teachers about the needs of students from marginalized communities, persons with disabilities and those requiring special assistance. Further, NEP 2020 underscores the importance of inculcating ethics and ethical principles in trainers, who will then impart these values to the students (National Education Policy, 2020 pp. 38-39).

Teacher Autonomy and Empowerment

The National Education Policy, 2020 recognizes the need for teacher autonomy in curriculum and instructional decisions. The policy suggests that by reducing administrative barriers and promoting collaborative learning practices, teachers will be enabled to focus on their fundamental duty and at the same time strive to facilitate important learning experiences.

Research and Innovation in Teacher Training

Teacher-education institutions will be urged to participate in educational research, policy analysis, and curriculum development to promote research and innovation. The National Education Policy, 2020 recommends a research-driven methodology in teacher education, which promotes evidence-based practices and policy reforms. The National Education Policy, 2020 provides a broad framework for improving teacher education in India. The policy seeks to establish a strong, competent and motivated teaching workforce with emphasis on high-quality teacher preparation, sustainable professional development, and empowerment of teachers. Effective implementation of these reforms will certainly enhance the inclusivity, innovation and vitality of the education system in India.

Efforts of the National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE)

The National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) is a statutory body established in 1995 pursuant to the NCTE Act (1993) to monitor and regulate teacher education in India. It works under the Ministry of Education (formerly Ministry of Human Resources) and its mandate is to guarantee the quality, uniformity and advancement of teacher education across the country. Over the years, NCTE has implemented several measures to improve teacher-education, promote professional development, and align educational standards with international best practices.

National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST)

NPST is a significant initiative of the National Education Policy, 2020, which aims to establish comprehensive recommendations for teacher competencies across multiple career stages. The NPST will

establish a standardized framework for teacher recruitment, performance appraisal, and professional development across India.

Four-Year Integrated Education Bachelor Program

As per the recommendations of the National Education Policy, 2020, NCTE has established a four-year integrated B.Ed. programme to replace the traditional teacher education model. This course combines graduate study with teacher preparation, providing information about training, practical teaching, practice, and pedagogical theory, providing an interdisciplinary and comprehensive educational approach. The Integrated Teacher Education Programme is full of various features covering humanities, science, yoga and commerce (NEP, 2020 page – 68-9).

The NEP 2020 highlights, “Teacher education is vital in creating a pool of school teachers that will shape the next generation. Teacher preparation is an activity that requires multidisciplinary perspectives and knowledge, formation of dispositions and values, and development of practice under the best mentors. Teachers must be grounded in Indian values, languages, knowledge, ethos, and traditions including tribal traditions, while also being well-versed in the latest advances in education and pedagogy” [Para 15.1, NEP 2020].

Reforms in Teacher-Education Institutions (TEIs)

NCTE has focused on enhancing the infrastructure and quality of teacher-education institutions across the country. Initiatives are ongoing to enhance the existing teacher training colleges and guarantee compliance with established requirements. It aims to establish better teacher-education institutions that offer a variety of teacher education programmes and research prospects (National Policy on Education, 2020 , p. 68).

Continuing Professional Development for Teachers (CPD)

NCTE advocates for organized sustainable professional development programs to assist teachers in making them aware of contemporary teaching methods and technology innovations. Collaboration with educational institutions and internet platforms provides teachers with readily available training possibilities. National Innovation and Research Network (NIRN) To advance research and innovation in teacher education, NCTE launched the NIRN programme. This network promotes collaborative research, exchange of best practices, and the formulation of policies in the education sector.

Use of Technology and Digital Platforms

NCTE has implemented digital technologies and e-learning platforms to improve teacher training and facilitate distance learning models. The initiative includes online training modules, digital assessments and virtual instructional simulations. The introduction of teacher-education resource platforms, such as Diksha and Swayam, provides educators with access to better learning materials.

Enhancing Internship and Practicum Experience

NCTE has updated its standards to improve practical training in teacher education programmes. The need for expanded and more organized internships in educational institutions with hands-on learning experience has now been identified for teacher-education programmes and comprehensive instructions have been given in this regard.

Regulations for Teacher Education (NCTE Regulations 2014)

In 2014, NCTE issued comprehensive guidelines for scaling up teacher education programmes. These regulations establish uniform admission standards, curriculum frameworks, faculty credentials and duration of teacher education programs. He also implemented compulsory accreditation of teacher-education institutions (TEIs).

Capacity Building Workshops, Special Education Training and Regular Training Sessions

NCTE continuously conducts capacity building workshops and seminars for teacher trainers and institutional leadership. These activities emphasize contemporary teaching techniques, educational research methodologies, and the efficient application of technology. Acceptance of Special Teacher Training Programmes: NCTE has accepted and implemented special teacher training programmes including curriculum for inclusive education and training for special education instructors. These programs cater to the diverse needs of learners and promote inclusive pedagogical methods. Protocol for Inclusive and Multilingual Education As per the National Education Policy, 2020, NCTE has implemented policies for educating teachers in multilingual instruction and inclusive pedagogical approach. Teachers are instructed to be attentive to the needs of diverse students from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds. NCTE has forged alliances and collaborations with global organizations and partnerships with international organizations for sharing best practices and knowledge in teacher-education. These collaborations emphasize the adoption of international norms and innovations within the Indian teacher education sector.

Performance Appraisal Report (PAR)

NCTE has provided Performance Appraisal Reports (PARs) to streamline the functioning of teacher education institutions and to ensure quality in each teacher education institution. Under this system, every teacher education institution will have to share its functioning, resources and arrangements with the NCTE on a regular basis and if any institution fails to do so, it may be debarred by the NCTE. This effort of NCTE seems to be very effective in regulating and controlling teacher education institutions.

Discussion and Conclusion

The teacher-education landscape in India has undergone significant changes, with the National Education Policy (NEP), 2020 representing a significant milestone in this area. The National Education Policy, 2020 introduces a revolutionary approach to teacher education, prioritizing excellent education, teacher preparation, and lifelong learning while at the same time ensuring alignment with global best practices and local needs. The National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) has played a pivotal role in planning and implementing these changes, ensuring that teacher education aligns with changing educational needs. The above analysis presents an in-depth analysis of the impact of the National Education Policy, 2020 and the initiatives of the National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) on the emerging importance of teacher education in India. The National Education Policy, 2020 outlines teacher education as an important area for improvement in terms of enhancing the overall quality of education in India. This policy underscores some of the difficulties within the current teacher-education system, such as fragmentation, low quality, inadequate practical performance, and limited opportunities for ongoing professional development. The National Education Policy recommends comprehensive steps to overcome these difficulties, which include the following:

- The National Education Policy, 2020 supports the establishment of a four-year Integrated Teacher - Education Programme (ITEP), which combines disciplinary knowledge with academic training. This initiative seeks to enhance the understanding of future educators of pedagogical techniques and subject-matter knowledge.
- This policy underscores the need to close independent teacher – education institutions, which fail to meet quality criteria. The National Education Policy, 2020 aims to establish a more comprehensive learning environment for future teachers by integrating teacher-education within multidisciplinary institutions.
- The policy emphasises the importance of continuous professional advancement for teachers. It recommends the establishment of opportunities for teachers to participate in ongoing training and

skill development initiatives, so that they can keep abreast of evolving educational trends and technologies.

- NEP emphasizes the importance of regular evaluation of licensing and teacher-education institutions to maintain better quality standards. It advocates for the creation of a transparent and stringent accreditation system.
- The policy advocates for integration of teacher education with multidisciplinary higher education institutions, which will facilitate teachers to engage in research and innovation.
- The National Education Policy, 2020 has transformed the paradigm of teacher education in India by emphasizing on comprehensive development of teaching professionals rather than mere certification. This change includes revisions to the curriculum, instructional strategies, assessment techniques, and professional development prospects. We can explore the changing importance of teacher education through the following points: The traditional emphasis on rote learning and didactic instruction is being replaced by creative and learner-centered approaches.
- Teacher education currently prioritizes critical thinking, problem-solving, and experience-based learning. As digital technologies become more prevalent in education, teacher-education programs are adding training on digital tools, online pedagogy, and technology-enhanced learning settings.
- NEP promotes a competency-based approach to teacher-education, emphasizing the development of specific skills and competencies required for effective teaching.
- Teacher Education is progressively prioritizing inclusive educational techniques to address the diverse needs of learners, including individuals with special educational needs.
- The amalgamation of teacher education with higher education institutions fosters a culture of study and innovation, which inspires teachers to examine innovative teaching approaches and educational practices.
- NEP, 2020 emphasizes on developing teachers as ethical and socially responsible professionals, contributing to nation-building and social cohesion.

National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) Initiatives to Improve Teacher Education

The National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) is important in regulating and standardizing teacher education in India. Established in the year 1993, NCTE has taken initiatives to improve the quality and relevance of teacher-education. Within the framework of the National Education Policy, 2020, NCTE has

implemented several measures to align teacher-education with the goals of the policy, some of the important ones being the following:

- NCTE has developed curriculum frameworks which are in line with NEP's focus on multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary education, research and broad learning.
- NCTE has enhanced its accreditation processes to ensure that teacher education institutions comply with the established quality standards. This includes regular exams and assessments.
- The NCTE has issued recommendations for execution of the four-year Integrated Teacher Education Programme which assures alignment with the targets set for Holistic Teacher Training.
- NCTE implements capacity building initiatives for teacher educators and administrators to improve their understanding of contemporary educational practices and technologies.
- NCTE engages with diverse stakeholders such as universities, state governments, and educational organizations to facilitate effective implementation of teacher-education reforms.
- NCTE advocates for research and innovation in teacher-education by providing funding and support for research initiatives and conferences.

Obstacles and Tips

While the initiatives of the National Education Policy, 2020 and the National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) have established a strong framework for positive change in teacher education in India, several obstacles remain, one of which is the need for the successful implementation of the recommendations of the National Education Policy, 2020. Coordinated efforts are required at the state and institutional levels. Comprehensive capacity building initiatives are needed to equip teacher-trainers and administrators with the necessary skills to implement innovative educational methods. Adequate financial and infrastructural resources are critical for effective implementation of teacher education changes. Controlling the opposition to change among teachers and institutions is essential for the successful implementation of new teaching approaches and practices. A comprehensive monitoring and evaluation system is essential to assess the effectiveness of teacher education programmes and identify areas for improvement.

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